

NEB Academy Hub Ukraine - Knowledge Gaps :: Preliminary Results

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Table of contents

Summary	2
About the initiative	2
About the InnoRenew CoE	2
About U-Lead with Europe	2
Data	3
Demographics	3
Age	3
Education	3
Occupation	3
Knowledge and importance	4
Visualisations	5
Topic: Design	5
Biomaterials	7
Buildings	9
Cultural Heritage	11
Digitisation	13
Policy and Standards	15
NEB	17

Summary

These are preliminary results of a survey being conducted in Ukraine to understand the the priority areas for a New European Bauhaus (NEB) Academy Hub to address as part of the *Rebuilding a Better Ukraine via the New European Bauhaus Academy (NEB Academy Hub Ukraine)* initiative.

Establishing the NEB Academy in Europe is under way. Prior to that initiative a survey was conducted to identify key knowledge gaps amongst different stakeholders across Europe. As efforts are now in progress to establish NEB Academy Hubs in Ukraine, a similar survey has been conducted via online questionnaire. These *preliminary* results are based on the results as of 03 November 2024.

The questionnaire was developed for purpose. It asks respondents to rate their current knowledge and their perception of the importance on several topics critical to sustainable construction and the NEB approach to building better.

About the initiative

The *Rebuilding a Better Ukraine via the New European Bauhaus Academy (NEB Academy Hub Ukraine)* initiative is implemented by the InnoRenew CoE and supported by the U-LEAD with Europe Programme.

About the InnoRenew CoE

InnoRenew CoE has been at the forefront of New European Bauhaus activities since its inception and has participated heavily in its development. It has been a key member of the Wood4Bauhaus alliance which has raised awareness about the benefits and availability of wood-based solutions for sustainable, beautiful, and inclusive buildings. It was a major contributor to the Horizon Europe – New European Bauhaus Nexus Report and now hosts the first pioneer hub of the New European Bauhaus Academy, the New European Bauhaus Academy Pioneer Hub for Sustainable Built Environments with Renewable Materials Hub (NEBAP Hub) of the University of Primorska.

About U-Lead with Europe

U-LEAD with Europe: Local Empowerment, Accountability and Development Programme is a multi-donor action of the EU and its member states Germany, Poland, Denmark and Slovenia to support Ukraine on its path to strengthening local self-government. U-LEAD promotes transparent, accountable, resilient and responsive multi-level governance in Ukraine and empowers municipalities.

Data

The data are being collected via an online questionnaire. It is available in the Ukrainian and English languages. These data were retrieved on 03 November 2024. To date, there are 60 complete responses and between 63 and 80 partial responses.

Demographics

Age

Table 1: Age

Topic	Label	Count
Age	25 - 35	37
Age	36 - 45	46
Age	46 - 55	28
Age	Over 55	13
Age	under 25	1

Education

Table 2: Education

Topic	Label	Count
Education	Bachelor's degree	12
Education	Doctorate degree	9
Education	High school graduate, diploma or equivalent	0
Education	Less than high school degree	0
Education	Master's degree	79
Education	Other:	7
Education	Professional degree	16
Education	Some college credit, no degree	1
Education	Trade, technical or vocational training	1

Occupation

Table 3: Occupation

Topic	Label	Count
Occupation	Architecture	15
Occupation	Civil service	19
Occupation	Construction	20
Occupation	Engineering	14
Occupation	Finance-banking	11
Occupation	Insurance	0
Occupation	Other:	31
Occupation	Policy-making	9
Occupation	Public procurement	2
Occupation	Real-estate development	4

Knowledge and importance

There are two basic ways to interpret the data at this stage:

1. Identify knowledge level and importance level to find where importance is greater than knowledge. These are primary areas to create trainings for. These are likely to be “popular” training topics.
2. Identify knowledge and importance level deficiencies in topics known to be important for to the NEB approach or sustainable building in general.

Visualisations

Topic: Design

Design :: Knowledge

Biomaterials

Biomaterials

Biomaterials :: Importance

Biomaterials :: Knowledge

Buildings

Buildings

Buildings :: Importance

Buildings :: Knowledge

Cultural Heritage

Cultural Heritage

Cultural Heritage :: Importance

Cultural Heritage :: Knowledge

Digitisation

Digitisation :: Knowledge

Policy and Standards

Policy and Standards :: Knowledge

NEB

New European Bauhaus

New European Bauhaus :: Importance

New European Bauhaus :: Knowledge

